

loam textured Entic Chromustert with $\text{KMnO}_4\text{-N}$ 110 ppm, 0.75% organic C, and pH 7.4. Test crop was ADT36, grown in 20-m² plots replicated 3 times in a randomized complete block design.

A 12.5- × 35-cm cylindrical frame covered with a polythene bag was placed between rows immediately after fertilizer application. A petri dish containing 100 ml of 0.1 N H_2SO_4 was suspended inside the frame. The dish was emptied at 3-d intervals and the contents distilled for NH_3 . Ammonia volatilization loss was calculated 15 d after basal application and after each topdressing (see table).

Values are after deducting loss in control plots. Correlations were worked out for pH, temperature, and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ content of floodwater with volatilization loss.

The cumulative N loss ranged from 3.44 to 5.85 kg/ha. The highest was with urea split application, followed by split-applied lac-coated urea. Green manure

Volatilization loss of N. TNRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1984.

Treatment	Loss of N (kg/ha)			Cumulative loss of N kg/ha
	Phase I 0-15 d	Phase II 16-30 d	Phase III 31-45 d	
Urea best split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4}$)	2.82	2.24	0.80	5.85
Urea all basal	3.13	1.28	0.50	4.95
Lac-coated urea (LCU) basal	2.89	1.35	0.48	4.72
Neem cake coated urea (NCU) basal	2.78	1.19	0.47	4.39
Green manure + urea (1 : 1) basal	2.20	1.11	0.47	3.78
LCU split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4}$)	2.34	2.15	0.57	5.06
NCU split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4}$)	1.71	1.88	0.74	4.33
Green manure + urea split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8}$)	1.18	1.79	0.48	3.44
Mean	2.37	1.62	0.57	
CD				0.47
% loss to the total loss	52	36	12	100

and urea combination had relatively lower loss than other N sources. Basal application showed higher losses than topdressings. Of the total volatilization loss, 52% occurred within 15 d, 36% between 15 and 30 d, and 12% between 31 and 45 d. NH_3 loss correlated with

morning floodwater pH ($r = 0.45^{**}$), evening floodwater pH ($r = 0.55^{**}$), morning floodwater temperature ($r = 0.49^{**}$), evening floodwater temperature ($r = 0.61^{**}$), and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ content of floodwater ($r = 0.43^{**}$). □

Response of upland rices to nitrogen

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Three upland rice varieties (Faro 11, E425 and R66) were planted on sandy loam soil with 0.09% total N, 1.63%

organic matter, and pH 5.4. N as ammonium sulfate was applied at 0, 30, and 60 kg N/ha, half at planting and half 60 d after. P and K were applied basally, each at 30 kg/ha.

Treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 12 m². Plant spacing was 30 × 30 cm.

Application of 60 kg N/ha did not significantly increase grain yield over 30 kg N/ha (Table 1). Stem borer damage and lodging percentage were higher with 60 kg N/ha.

Varieties tested were similar in all parameters examined (Table 2). □

Table 1. Effect of N level on yield, yield components, and growth of rice.^a Ibadan, Nigeria, 1984.

N level (kg/ha)	Yield (kg/plot)	Lodging ^b (%)	Whiteheads (no./plot)	Wt of 10 panicles (g)	Plant ht ^b (cm)	Tillers ^b (no./hill)
0	1.64 b	0	31 b	46 b	102 b	14 b
30	1.94 a	31	41 b	50 b	111 a	15 b
60	1.98 a	78	91 a	62 a	113 a	16 a

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b Recorded at maturity. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Varietal differences in yield, yield components, and growth of rice. Ibadan, Nigeria, 1984.

Variety	Yield (kg/plot)	Lodging (%)	Days to 50% flowering	Whiteheads (no./plot)	Wt of 10 panicles (g)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)
Faro 11	1.87	39	87	55	52	107	15
E425	1.93	36	88	53	53	108	15
R66	1.78	33	88	54	52	110	15
LSD (0.05)	ns	-	-	ns	ns	ns	ns

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Relationship between organic N fraction and N uptake of rice in submerged soil

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A field experiment during the 1983-84 wet season showed that hydrolyzable